

ANALYSIS OF ELECTRON DISTRIBUTION AND CHEMICAL BONDING AT THE INTERFACE REGION OF SI(001)/AL₂O₃(001), SI(001)/TiO₂(001), AND SI(001)/SiO₂(001) HETEROSTRUCTURES

¹D. Sh. Kurbanov, ²K. R. Yakubov, ³R. B. Bazarbayev, ⁴R. Sh. Rahimboyev, ⁵S. Zh. Karazhanov, ⁶A. A. Vardiyashvili

^{1,2,3,4}Urganch State University, Urganch, Uzbekistan

⁵Department of Solar Energy, Institute of Energy Technology, Instituttveien 18, 2027 Kjeller, Norway

⁶Karshi State University, Karshi, Uzbekistan

¹[0000-0003-1557-9927], ²[0000-0002-7577-943X], ³[0000-0002-2769-0908], ⁴[0009-0006-5123-8045], ⁵[0000-0001-6504-2517], ⁶[0009-0005-9852-7269]

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15430291>

All calculations were performed using the Vienna Ab initio Simulation Package (VASP 6.5) [11, 14], employing the Projector Augmented Wave (PAW) method [13, 14, 15] parameterized by Perdew, Burke, and Ernzerhof (PBE) [9] within the generalized gradient approximation (GGA). Spin polarization was considered to accurately obtain the system energy. A cutoff energy of 620 eV was used. For geometry optimization, force and energy convergence criteria of 0.02 eV/Å and 10⁻⁵ eV, respectively, were employed. For sampling the Brillouin zone, Gamma-centered k-point meshes of 2 × 3 × 1, 2 × 4 × 1, and 2 × 3 × 1 were used for Si(001)/Al₂O₃(001), Si(001)/TiO₂(001), and Si(001)/SiO₂(001), respectively [9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15].

Before creating the Si(001)/TiO₂(001), Si(001)/SiO₂(001), and Si(001)/Al₂O₃(001) heterostructure interfaces, the lattice parameters of the Si, SiO₂, Al₂O₃, and TiO₂ unit cells were optimized. For their optimization, Gamma-centered k-point meshes of Si(5 × 5 × 5), SiO₂(9 × 9 × 5), Al₂O₃(9 × 9 × 2) and TiO₂(7 × 7 × 3) were used. The optimized unit cell lattice parameters are Si (a = b = c = 5.4659 Å), Al₂O₃ (a = 4.76 Å, b = 4.76 Å, c = 13.004 Å), SiO₂ (a = 4.83 Å, b = 4.83 Å, c = 5.359 Å), and TiO₂ (a = 3.801 Å, b = 3.801 Å, c = 9.5 Å), respectively. The calculated lattice parameter values are in good agreement with experimental data [16, 17, 18, 19]. Supercells were constructed from the optimized lattice parameters, and then the Si(001)/TiO₂(001), Si(001)/SiO₂(001), and Si(001)/Al₂O₃(001) interfacial heterostructures were created. The lattice mismatch was minimized by adjusting the in-plane lattice parameters. The Si(001)/Al₂O₃(001), Si(001)/TiO₂(001), and Si(001)/SiO₂(001) heterostructures were optimized using 2 × 3 × 1, 2 × 4 × 1, and 2 × 3 × 1 Gamma-centered k-point meshes, respectively.

After optimizing the heterostructures, several changes occurred in the interface region. Specifically, in the ELF analysis of Si(001)/Al₂O₃(001), Si–O–Al bonding emerged at the interface. Electron density is concentrated around O atoms, while Si and Al lost electrons. Consequently, Si and Al became positive ions, and oxygen became a negative ion. This reflects strong ionic bonding. Bader charge analysis also confirms this. The high electronegativity of oxygen tends to attract electrons, which, in bonds involving metal oxides like Al₂O₃ and TiO₂, leads to an ionic character through local charge accumulation. The transfer of -1.378 e and -1.23 e charge to the interface oxygen atoms indicates the accumulation of excess electrons. The largest charge loss from the silicon surface also corresponds to the Si(001)/Al₂O₃(001) interface. At the interfaces of the other heterostructures, interfacial bonding also occurred via oxygen

(Figures 3, 4). Looking at the ELF for Si(001)/TiO₂(001), the electron loss around Ti indicates the absence of strongly localized electron pairs around it. In the Bader charge analysis of Si(001)/TiO₂(001), we observe that $-1.27 e$ charge transferred to the key oxygen atom forming the Si–O–Ti interfacial bond. We can also observe similar charge transfer characteristics in the regions corresponding to Al in the Si(001)/Al₂O₃(001) interface. In the Si(001)/SiO₂(001) heterostructure, the surfaces are bonded via Si–O–Si and Si–Si bonds. This indicates that the surfaces are bonded through both ionic (Si–O–Si) and covalent (Si–Si) type bonds in the interface region. At the Si(001)/Al₂O₃(001) interface, bonding occurred primarily via Si–O–Al bonds with a pronounced ionic character. In all heterostructures, on the Si(001) side, the ELF plots show electron localization in the region between Si atoms, indicating the presence of covalent bonding character within the silicon substrate near the interface. If we consider the Bader charge distribution among the silicon atoms directly at the Si(001) interface surface across all considered heterostructures, the values suggest charge transfer consistent with the formation of polar bonds, approaching ionic interactions with the oxide layers. The Bader charges of the key oxygen atoms forming bonds at the Si(001)/Al₂O₃(001), Si(001)/TiO₂(001), and Si(001)/SiO₂(001) interfaces were found to be $-1.378 e$ and $-1.23 e$, $-1.27 e$, and $-1.273 e$, respectively.

Through a combined analysis of ELF and Bader charges, we determined the nature of bonding and charge transfer at the Si(001)/TiO₂(001), Si(001)/SiO₂(001), and Si(001)/Al₂O₃(001) interfaces. The Si(001)/SiO₂(001) interface exhibits a high degree of electron localization with both ionic (Si–O–Si) and covalent (Si–Si) bonding character, which underlies its unique interface properties. In contrast, in the Si(001)/TiO₂(001) heterostructure, Si atoms on the silicon surface and Ti atoms on the TiO₂ surface are bonded via oxygen. Localized electrons accumulated around the oxygen atoms. In Si(001)/Al₂O₃(001), the accumulation of electrons was also found to correspond to oxygen in the interface region. The Si(001)/Al₂O₃(001) and Si(001)/TiO₂(001) heterojunctions show evidence of strong ionically characterized bonding at the interface. The largest charge loss from the silicon surface corresponded to Si(001)/Al₂O₃(001). The Bader charges of the key oxygen atoms involved in bonding at the Si(001)/Al₂O₃(001), Si(001)/TiO₂(001), and Si(001)/SiO₂(001) interfaces were $-1.378 e$ and $-1.23 e$, $-1.27 e$, and $-1.273 e$, respectively. These atomistic calculations yielded fundamentally important results for designing next-generation Si/oxide devices. The obtained results serve as an important scientific factor for selecting optimized variants in the development of modern electronic devices and high-sensitivity gas sensors.